

Low Pressure Negative Chemical Ionisation Mass Spectra of Friedelane Derivatives†

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Low pressure negative chemical ionisation mass spectra of several C₃₀ and C₂₇ oxygenated friedelanes have been studied using sodium bicarbonate to generate the reagent ions. Ionisation and fragmentation are directed by the functional groups present. Intense (M-H)⁻ ion and a few structurally diagnostic fragment ion peaks are observed. The presence of carbonyl function at C₁₃ or C₁₄ leads to fragments originating via γ -H rearrangement.

UNLIKE positive ion chemical ionisation mass spectra which require the use of a 'tight' ion source, negative ion chemical ionisation mass spectra can be obtained at considerably lower pressures using conventional electron impact source¹. Reagent gases can be generated *in situ* in the ion source from appropriate reagents²⁻⁴. Negative ion spectra are very sensitive to the background ions in the source. The presence of a known reagent ion(s) in the source thus helps in obtaining reproducible spectra⁵. Reports on the negative ion spectra of naturally occurring compounds are scarce in literature. As a continuation of our earlier work on the negative ion spectra of triterpenoids^{6,7}, we have undertaken the present investigation of the mass spectral behaviour of a series of friedelane derivatives (1-14) under low pressure negative chemical ionisation conditions using the sodium bicarbonate technique⁴.

Experimental

The compounds used in this study were either natural products isolated from *Putranjiva roxburghii* or their chemically modified derivatives^{8,9}. The mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol D-300 mass spectrometer having a negative ion detection unit and attached to JMA-2000 data system. The samples mixed with a small amount of sodium bicarbonate were introduced into the electron impact ion source through the direct inlet system and heated to 200°. The spectra were recorded during the evolution of CO₂ as indicated by the source housing pressure rising to approximately 2 × 10⁻⁵ torr⁴. The other ion source conditions were, electron energy 70 eV, emission current 300 μ A, and temperature 200°.

Results and Discussion

The positive ion electron impact spectra of friedelane derivatives have been studied by several

workers⁸⁻¹¹. Presence of methyl groups at C₁₃ and C₁₄ makes friedelanes susceptible to fragmentation by cleavages of rings C and D. Consequently most of the total ion current is carried by D and E ring containing fragments. In contrast, the negative ion spectra of 1-14 (Table 1) show very little fragmentation except in a few cases. Apart from the acetates 4 and 14 and the diketone 8, all the other compounds give abundant (M-H)⁻ ions (base peak). The reagent ions O⁻ and OH⁻ can abstract a proton either from the hydroxyl group or from the CH or CH₂ group α to the carbonyl function. Compounds containing hydroxy groups (1-3) show (M-3)⁻ ions, presumably resulting from the oxidation of the alcohol to ketone. Varying amounts of (M-15)⁻, (M-17)⁻ and (M-19)⁻ ions are also observed in the spectra of most of these compounds.

The ion at *m/z* 367 is common to the 7-keto compounds. This ion is accompanied by minor ions at *m/z* 368 and 355. Scheme 1 shows the probable

Scheme 1

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formation of these ions. The fragment ions at m/z 205 in 8 and 9, at m/z 191 in 7 and at m/z 207 in 3 most likely arise by a γ -hydrogen rearrangement involving C_6 or C_{14} methyl hydrogen as it is observed only in the 7-keto compounds (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

- (1) $R_1=R_2=H, \alpha-OH$
- (2) $R_1=O; R_2=H, \alpha-OH$
- (3) $R_1=H, \alpha-OH; R_2=O$
- (4) $R_1=H, \alpha-OAc; R_2=O$
- (5) $R_1=O-OH_2-CH_2-O;$
 $R_2=H, \alpha-OH$
- (6) $R_1=O; R_2=H_2$
- (7) $R_1=H_2; R_2=O$
- (8) $R_1=R_2=O$
- (9) $R_1=O-OH_2-CH_2-O;$
 $R_2=O$
- (10) $R_1=NOH; R_2=O$
- (11) $R=CO_2H$
- (12) $R=CO_2Me$

In the positive ion spectra the corresponding McLafferty rearrangement ions appear at two mass units higher^{8,9}. The 3-keto compounds are characterised by the appearance of an intense ion at m/z 71. One of the pathways for the formation of this ion also probably involves a γ -hydrogen rearrangement (Scheme 3). The presence of carbonyl groups at both C_8 and C_7 considerably enhances the abundance of this ion (m/z 71 is the base peak in 8).

In the ketals 5 and 9, loss of C_8H_4O from the $(M-H)^-$ ion results in the generation of the corresponding ketone. Another characteristic feature in the spectra of the ketals is the appearance of a peak corresponding to $(M-99)^-$. It is interesting to note here that the complementary ion at m/z 99 gives rise to the base peak in the positive ion spectra of these ketals, thus showing the complementary nature

TABLE 1—RELATIVE ION ABUNDANCES (%) IN THE NEGATIVE ION SPECTRA OF 1-14

Ions	Compound (Mol. wt.)													
	1 (444)	2 (442)	3 (442)	4 (484)	5 (486)	6 (426)	7 (426)	8 (440)	9 (484)	10 (455)	11 (456)	12 (470)	13 (446)	14 (530)
$(M-1)^-$	100	100	100	14.7	100	100	100	95	100	100	100	100	100	1.0
$(M-2)^-$	9.2	8.0	12.7	1.4	15.6	10.0	9.7	4.0	5.0	3.0	9.1	2.0	—	—
$(M-3)^-$	7.2	8.0	34.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
$(M-15)^-$	—	11.4	7.0	1.8	—	15.0	—	8.7	—	—	—	9.3	—	—
$(M-17)^-$	2.2	10.8	9.3	—	—	15.0	21.1	12.5	6.4	32.3	6.4	5.3	—	—
$(M-19)^-$	—	10.8	15.4	—	—	—	—	12.6	—	6.0	—	—	25.0	—
$(M-99)^-$	—	—	—	—	19.2	—	—	—	27.0	—	—	—	—	—
m/z 367	—	—	13.3	0.5	—	—	—	24.2	3.0	18.3	—	—	—	—
m/z 71	—	48.3	—	—	36.4	42.5	—	100	60.0	—	14.1	25.0	—	—
m/z 59	—	—	—	100	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	100
Other ions			421 (17.0)	441 (3.8)	441 (35.8)	—	191 (5.8)	368 (26.5)	439 (26.5)	368 (8.1)	428 (4.0)	437 (9.2)	—	427 (0.5)
			968 (6.5)	423 (2.6)	—	—	—	355 (14.0)	355 (4.3)	355 (4.0)	411 (2.0)	409 (3.3)	—	—
			955 (5.0)	—	—	—	—	205 (9.3)	205 (4.4)	163 (14.2)	409 (5.3)	99 (15.0)	—	—
			207 (8.2)	—	—	—	—	—	—	86 (42.4)	99 (15.2)	—	—	—
			205 (4.0)	—	—	—	—	—	—	85 (11.6)	—	—	—	—

Only ions having m/z values >50 reported. Reagent ions at m/z 16 and 17 and background ions (due to halogens) excluded.

of positive and negative ion spectra. In the acetates **4** and **14** most of the ion current is carried by the acetoxy ion as expected for acetoxy compounds^{6,7}. The diol (**13**) fragments only by the loss of water from the $(M-H)^-$ ion.

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